

FERNET : Symmetric Key Encryption for Password Security

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Abstract: Fernet is a symmetric key encryption cryptographic method that is mainly used for password encryption and decryption. It secures the password more safely. But the main problem faces by many users that is about hacking. This paper gives awareness about how to secure our details by using fernet algorithm. Thus we can make Fernet more powerful and we can take more security steps to prevent it from hackers and intruders.

Key Words: fernet, fernet token, key, generate_key(), encrypt_data()

I. INTRODUCTION

Fernet is a python http server script that creates powerful pages and secures the details property. And it is also secure stored data in the device. It works just like AES first we generate the key, encryption of plaintext to cipher text, and decryption of cipher text to plaintext using the encrypt and decrypt methods. simply it takes credentials from users when they type confidential information like usernames, passwords, each password has its own symmetric key . which makes sure that the message encrypted cannot be manipulated/read without the key. And all the details secured in this key. A fernet token is the base64url encoding. The fernet module of the cryptography package has inbuilt functions that is for generation of the key, encryption of plaintext to cipher text, and decryption of cipher text to plaintext using the encrypt and decrypt methods . With a cryptographic package that support by Python to encrypt and decrypt data. The fernet system module gives more guarantee and safety that data encrypted using it cannot be manipulated or read without the key. Each data has its own key and by only using this key we can decrypt the data. Encryption does not itself prevent interference but rejects the intelligible content to a would-be interceptor. Here, the fernet system generates a fresh fernet key. Keep it someplace safe. If you lose, then not able to decrypt messages. Plain text passwords are kept directly during

info with no encryption. These passwords are insecure because, If somebody hacks your database he will access any account and do something attainable once log in. - Developers or workers who are performing on a project usually misuse the password and unfold these passwords to others for misuse thus encryption helps us by protecting information from hackers. Cryptography deals with the secret writing of plaintext to cipher text and decryption of cipher text to plaintext. If you consider the needs of encryption algorithm. Passwords are stored in the database, so we can use traditional methods to protect them to prevent access to the database in a completely secure way, such as firewalls, role definitions, etc. We need to provide additional protection by converting the password into an unreadable (encrypted) format. To understand password encryption, we need to understand that plain text passwords and these types of passwords are insecure. The plain text password is stored directly in the database without encryption. These passwords are very insecure because the person who hacked into your database can access any account and can perform any operations after logging in. Project personnel often abuse passwords and pass these passwords to others to abuse the passwords. Encryption allows us to protect data from hacker attacks.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Zyrian[1] and Haga[2] have researched in the California Department about password security defense. The questionnaire was sent by 997 participants. Zviran and Haga in 1999 found that 24.9% of respondents used 6-digit passwords. Haga in 1999 also found that 80.1% of respondents' passwords only contain letters. Zviran and Haga found that most passwords chosen by users are based on the characteristics of personal data. These characteristics are very important to individuals, are short, consist of alphanumeric characters, and are not frequently

changed and frequently entered. In other words, the password is still easy to remember, and structure are simple. Zviran and Haga observed an increase in the frequency of password changes. Although the password increases the security level, it makes it difficult to remember, and so on. End users tend to use short and simple passwords based on meaningful details. End users tend to use short, simple passwords based on meaningful details like Zviran and Haga.

If a hacker can access one account, he can access other accounts. The password is almost effortless. Using encrypted passwords, many sites store encrypted forms of passwords in their server databases. A special key used to convert a password into a random text string. The advantage of this is that without the key, hackers cannot obtain the password. All that can be obtained is a randomly encrypted string. The disadvantage is that the key is usually stored on the same server as the password. Therefore, if the server is attacked and the key is recovered, all passwords will be cracked and destroyed. Encryption is reversible, and the fact that messages can be encrypted and decrypted brings security risks. Fernet guarantees that the message encrypted with the message cannot be processed or read without the key. Create new Fernet key and Store in a safe place. If it is lost, no more messages can be decrypted. If other people can access it, they can decrypt all your messages and forge authenticated and decrypted random messages. The result of encryption is called "Fernet token". Then, you can decrypt the Fernet token. If the decryption is successful, you will receive the original plain text.

III. EASE OF USE

A. Provide more security

By using fernet symmetric method it provide more securely. When we set our password and other information to the storage the password they entered is in encrypted format and though the details being safely kept. And each password has its own key.

B. Avoid or Reject all hacking activity

No one such as hackers or intruders cannot access to someone details and also doesn't have to change their password or decrypt it through using another key. Because it uses URL for safe encoding for the keys and also uses 128 bit AES. So each password has its own consecutive keys. All the encrypted passwords are as a parameter basis. No one cannot login into their profile and hack it.

IV. IMPLIMENTATION

All the data can be secured by fernet algorithm. It is a crypto graphical method which is used for secure the useful information when data transmitting from one computer to another computer. And it is also secure stored data in the device. It mainly deals with the encryption of plaintext to cipher text and also decryption of cipher text to plaintext.. Any fraud actions can be restricted completely. Given a key and message, generate a fernet token. First we Record the current time for the timestamp field. And then construct the cipher text and the Encrypt the padded message using AES 128. We get a key and token, to verify that the token is valid and recover the original message data. Given a key and token, to verify that the token is valid and recover the original message and we have to Unpad the decrypted plaintext, yielding the original message. The system secures the details of all users by encrypting the password with secret key by using fernet algorithm. Two steps can be used in this method.

First , key generaton : The first generate key method generates a fernet key. The key been kept safely because it is the most important component to decrypt the cipher text. When the key is lost then the user cannot have to decrypt the message. Also when an intruder or hacker or any fraud gets access to the key they can not only read the data but also forge the data. The function is given by generate_key().

Second, Data Encryption: The encrypted data is passed as a parameter to the method. The output of this type of encryption is known as a "Fernet token" which is cipher text. The encrypted fernet token contains the current timestamp .when it has been generated in plaintext. The encryption method gives an exception when the data is not in bytes. Its function is given as encrypt(data).The encrypted data can be encrypted using the key.

Fig 1:Block diagram of implementation

Below given the important steps during generation

First we given the key and message, then generate a fernet token with the following steps.

1. We record the current time for the timestamp field.
2. Then a unique IV chosen.
3. Then we have to construct the cipher text.

And then we Pad the message to a multiple of 16 bytes is 128 bits per RFC 5652, This is the same padding technique used in PKCS #7 v1.5 and all versions of SSL/TLS.

After the padded messages can be encrypted using AES 128 in CBC mode with the chosen IV and user supplied encryption-key.

1. First Compute HMAC field as we described above using the user supplied signing-key. .
2. Then all the fields have been concatenated together.
3. Given base64 url that encode the entire token.

Steps involved in Verifying

Then given a key and token, used to verify that the token is valid and we then recover the original message, it perform the following steps.

4. The base64 url decode the token
5. We have to ensure that the first byte of the token is 0x80
6. While the user has specified a maximum "time-to-live" for the token that ensure the recorded timestamp is not too far in the past.
7. Then we have to recompute the HMAC from the some other fields and then the user-supplied signing key.
8. Cipher text field has been decrypted using AES 128 in CBC mode with the recorded IV and user-supplied encryption key.
9. Finally we unpad the decrypted plaintext, and then get the original message.

Format of Key

Fernet key is base64 url encoding of the below given fields. Such as Signing- key , Encryption-key ,Signing key-128 bits Encryption key- 128 bits

┆ Token Format

A fernet token is the base64url encoding of the concatenation of the following fields:

┆ Version

This field defines which version of the format is being used by the tokens. Currently there is only one version with the value 128 that is 0x80.

┆ Timestamp

This field is a 64-bit unsigned bigendian integer.

┆ HMAC

The field is 256-bit SHA256 HMAC that is under signing-key.

Fig 2: encryption of password using key.

V. CONCLUSION

Fernet, a symmetric key cryptographic method used for password security. When we set our password and other information to the storage the password they entered is in encrypted format and though the details being safely kept. And each password has its own key. So no one such as hackers or intruders cannot access to

their details and also doesn't have to change their password or decrypt it through using another key..It is mainly perform in the login activity and password setting activity. All have their own identification id and it contain all information .It is a cryptographic method that we used which is mainly secure the useful information when data transmitting from one computer to another computer. And it is also secure stored data in our device and it cannot be manipulated or read without the key. Each data has its own key and by only using

this key we can decrypt the data . Any fraud actions can be restricted completely.

VI. REFERENCE

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